

On the effect of popular additive manufacturing technologies on the performance and noise emission of UAV propellers

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Abstract

Noise remains a major concern for the widespread employment of Unmanned Air Vehicles (UAVs) operations, especially in urban environments. Moreover, not only must overall noise levels be considered when analyzing the acoustic impact of UAVs, but noise quality based on the spectral content of the acoustic signal must also be considered due to the psycho-acoustic effect on the listeners. Additionally, as UAVs become widespread, the ability to perform field replacement of propellers using additive manufacturing (AM) is of increased interest to many operators. However, as different AM techniques become popular, their impact on performance and noise must be assessed. In this investigation, the effect of manufacturing characteristics, such as surface roughness and flexibility, on the propeller thrust, torque, and acoustic signature is explored through an experimental campaign, revealing differences depending on the selected technique. A numerical experiment is then performed to isolate the effect of flexibility and roughness on these characteristics.

Keywords: Propellers; UAV; Acoustics; FDM; SLS; SLA;

1. Introduction

Unmanned Air Vehicles' (UAVs) popularity as an aerial platform for a wide range of civil and military applications continues to increase. From recreational purposes to surveillance and fire safety, passing through filmmaking, infrastructure inspection, road traffic control, cell network enhancement, to name a few, these aircraft are becoming widespread in both the countryside and urban spaces [1].

However, even though the technology in terms of flight performance is mature, its full potential, given all the described applications, is not yet fully realized, partly due to a combination of regulatory, safety, and acceptability concerns. On the first two fronts, several initiatives in the US, EU, UK, etc., aim to achieve a harmonized regulation that allows the safe operation of UAVs [2]. However, there are still some concerns about the public acceptability of UAV operations. Different public opinion surveys conducted by aviation authorities have found that UAV noise is one of the leading factors among these concerns [3].

When studying UAV noise, two aspects should be considered. On the one hand, there is the issue of overall noise level, which is the added global level that continued UAV operation could bring into homes, schools, hospitals, etc. According to the findings of the World Health Organization (WHO), noise levels are the second most harmful form of environmental cause of health problems, just after chemical pollutants [4]. Thus, care should be taken that the new

services provided by using UAVs do not increase these noise levels and their health consequences for the population. On the other hand, the psycho-acoustic impact of UAV noise signatures has been attested. Due to the particular flight dynamics of UAVs, based on multi-propeller speed control, the frequency content of the noise presents a semi-random variance around an average, often perceived as especially annoying [3, 5]. Therefore, both overall noise level and frequency content must be studied to address these concerns properly.

Consequently, the amount of research in propeller aeroacoustics has increased considerably in latter years. Recently, a benchmark for low Reynolds number propellers has been proposed [6]. Other works have focused on evaluating the accuracy of different numerical methods comparing different blade resolved methods with BEMT solutions [7, 8], or with the actuator line method [9]. The influence of non-axial inflow conditions on the acoustic performance has been also explored both experimentally [10] and numerically [11]. In addition, aerodynamic and aeroacoustic propeller-propeller and propeller-fuselage interactions have also been studied for both multicopters [12] and fixed-wing UAVs [13, 14].

Because of the low Reynolds at which these propellers operate, certain phenomena like laminar separation bubbles become important [15, 16]. Moreover, broadband noise becomes more relevant, so efforts are being made to improve the accuracy of numerical methods [17, 18]. The influence of the Additive Manufacturing (AM) technology used to manufacture the propeller has proven to have an impact on

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58 this broadband noise [17, 19].

59 In parallel with UAVs, another technology that is be-
60 coming widespread is Additive Manufacturing (AM). Since
61 UAVs are often subjected to crashes or forced landings,
62 which may imply a degree of damage, and given that the
63 propellers are often the most easily damaged part, rapid
64 in-field replacement of these components becomes an ex-
65 tremely desirable capability for many kinds of operators
66 [20]. For example, UAVs are being used to deliver medical
67 supplies in remote locations or even embarked on ocean-
68 going vessels. Obtaining spare parts such as propellers
69 from the UAV manufacturer is difficult or impossible in these
70 situations, and thus, the ability to rapidly manufacture
71 them from a supply of raw material becomes highly desirable.

72 However, replacing a commercial propeller with a 3D-
73 printed one is not straightforward, even if the geometry
74 is exactly the same. As different AM techniques result in
75 pieces with distinct mechanical properties such as flexibil-
76 ity, surface finish, roughness, anisotropy, etc., there is no
77 certainty that the performance of a recreated propeller, in
78 terms of thrust, torque, and noise emission, is equivalent
79 to that of the original. Previous works [17, 21, 22, 23] have
80 proven that hover performance and noise emissions are af-
81 fected by the AM technology used, but further work needs
82 to be done to fully comprehend these effects under differ-
83 ent operating conditions and for the entire noise spectrum.
84 To address this issue, in this investigation, we consider one
85 wooden commercial propeller typical of UAVs (XOAR 9x7)
86 and recreate it using the three most widespread AM tech-
87 niques, expanding the results presented by García-Tíscar
88 et al. [24]. All the proposed propellers have been tested
89 at CMT's anechoic chamber and wind tunnel to assess the
90 impact of the different AM methods on thrust, torque, and
91 noise emission, including overall level, directivity, and spec-
92 tral content. Since each technique introduces its particular
93 combination of mechanical properties, a numerical simu-
94 lation campaign is performed, in which each mechanical
95 property of the material is modified separately, allowing
96 a better understanding of their impact on the propeller
97 performance.

98 The present paper is structured as follows: this section
99 provides a brief introduction to the subject and a contextual-
100 ization of the current state-of-the-art of the field. Section 2
101 presents the propeller used, the additive manufacturing
102 techniques evaluated, the experimental setup, and the nu-
103 merical approach. Section 3 shows and discusses the ex-
104 perimental results, and the conclusions obtained from the
105 numerical analysis. Finally, in Section 4, the final conclu-
106 sions reached are summarized.

Figure 1: Workflow of the scanning, meshing and manufacturing of the propellers used in this work. Top image courtesy of UAV Works Group.

2. Methodology

2.1. Selected propeller

The commercial wooden XOAR PJN 9x7" (22.86 cm) propeller was selected for this research. This model of propeller is typical of fixed-wing UAVs such as the VALAQ120 by the UAV Works Group. In order to create the additive-manufactured (AM) versions of the propeller, the geometry

Figure 2: Conceptual schematic of the FDM technology.

114 of the propeller was extracted by manually fine-tuning a
115 structured-light 3D scanner digital model. Figure 1 depicts
116 the aforementioned process.

117 2.2. Additive manufacturing

118 The term Additive Manufacturing (AM), also known
119 popularly as 3D printing, encompasses a large variety of
120 very different technologies. Each technology has its own
121 strong points and weaknesses, especially in terms of me-
122 chanical properties and surface finish of the resulting items.
123 In this investigation, three of the most popular technolo-
124 gies have been selected, which are briefly described in this
125 subsection.

126 2.2.1. Fused Deposition Modeling (FDM)

127 Fused Deposition Modeling (FDM), also known as Fused
128 Filament Fabrication (FFF), is probably the most well-known
129 AM technology and can be considered as the one kickstart-
130 ing its recent popularity. In its essence, a continuous fila-
131 ment of thermoplastic material is extruded through a heated
132 printing head, which causes the material to melt or soften
133 enough to fuse with the previously deposited material. The
134 extruder head is continuously moved as required to form the
135 geometry of the desired item. Figure 2 shows this process.

136 The movements of the extruded heads are pre-computed
137 through software called *slicers* because the typical approach
138 is to “slice” the item geometry into a series of horizontal
139 planes. Commonly, the head will complete all the required
140 XY movements in each Z plane before moving to the next
141 one, which is typically accomplished by lowering the build-
142 ing platform itself. This process results in a manufactured
143 item that clearly shows the different Z layers in its surface
144 finish, in addition to possible “Z seams” resulting from the
145 filament extrusion’s starting and finishing points at each
146 layer. Moreover, the overhanging parts of the geometry
147 require supporting material that needs to be removed in
148 postprocessing steps.

149 In addition, the process of building the object through
150 subsequent Z layers of fused or deposited cordons of thermo-
151 plastic filament results in anisotropic mechanical properties,
152 as the behavior in the Z direction is usually quite different
153 from that of the X and Y directions. Furthermore, objects
154 are not fully filled even if 100% infill is selected, as the 3D
155 space cannot be filled by the cylindrical geometry of the
156 filaments.

157 2.2.2. Selective Laser Sintering (SLS)

158 SLS technology solves many of the common issues of
159 FDM. In this approach, a high-power, orientable laser melts
160 small particles of the building material (typically a polyamide
161 such as PA11 or PA12), fusing them together to form a
162 solid object. Again, the process involves slicing the object
163 into Z planes, as the laser can only traverse the XY plane.
164 Powdered material from a reservoir is thinly spread over a
165 movable bed through a roller, where the laser sinters the

166 required slice. Then, the bed is lowered, a fresh and un-
167 sintered powder layer is spread on top, and the process
168 repeats until the object has been fully built. The process is
169 shown in Fig. 3.

170 This technique presents several advantages. First, the
171 resulting object has practically isotropic mechanical proper-
172 ties, as the powder particles have fused together. Also, the
173 surface resolution is better than that of the FDM process, as
174 it is not limited by the geometry of the deposited filaments
175 but by the effective size of the laser. Finally, as the sintered
176 material is supported by the unsintered powder, no support
177 material is required. In fact, very complex and interlocking
178 geometries can be produced by taking advantage of this
179 fact.

180 However, this method is not without disadvantages.
181 First and foremost, the requirement of a high-powered laser
182 increases the complexity and cost of the machine, restricting
183 its use to more professional settings rather than hobby or
184 household environments. Working with powdered material
185 can also be a nuisance, and require procedures and/or a
186 dedicated workshop. The surface finish is usually rough,
187 even if it is free of visible Z layers or seams.

188 2.2.3. Stereolithography (SLA)

189 Finally, the SLA technique relies on the photopolymer-
190 ization of resin. When a UV light source is focused on the
191 bottom of a vat containing photopolymer resin, the resin
192 solidifies through a photochemical process. The laser is
193 steered to solidify the Z slice as required, and then, the liq-
194 uid vat is lowered and the laser draws the next slice, which
195 is fused with the previous one, as shown in Fig. 4.

196 Through this process, layering or seam effects are greatly
197 reduced. Also, the resulting pieces exhibit isotropic me-
198 chanical properties. Nowadays, SLA machines are more
199 accessible than SLS ones. Furthermore, a wide array of
200 resins with different properties is available, although the
201 material choice is not as varied as with FDM.

202 A variant of this technique uses a projector to shine
203 the complete image of each slice into the resin vat, which
204 lowers the cost of the machine even more. These are known
205 as Digital Light Processing (DPL) machines. However, the
206 projects work by projecting a raster image (made up of

Figure 3: Conceptual schematic of the SLS technology.

Table 1: Mechanical properties of the additive manufacturing materials used in this study [25, 26, 27, 28].

Property	Unit	FDM: ABS-M30	SLS: Nylon 12	SLA: Grey v4 (PC)	SLA: Rigid (PC)
Tensile modulus XZ	GPa	2.4			
Tensile modulus ZX	GPa	2.3	1.85	2.8	4.1
Flexural modulus XZ	GPa	2.22			
Flexural modulus ZX	GPa	1.96	1.6	2.2	3.4
Ultimate tensile strength XZ	MPa	28.1			
Ultimate tensile strength ZX	MPa	26.8	50	65	69
Flexural strength XZ	MPa	-			
Flexural strength ZX	MPa	47.7	66	-	-
Tens. elongation at break X/Y	%	8.1	11	6	5.3
Tens. elongation at break Z	%	1.8	6	6	
Heat Deflection Temp 0.45 Mpa	°C	103.8	171	73	77
Heat Deflection Temp 1.8 Mpa	°C	99.9	87	58	60

pixels) instead of the continuous movement of the laser spot of SLA machines. Thus, DPL results in pieces exhibiting a certain voxel effect, as if constructed of tiny cubes.

While SLA presents certain advantages, it also has some drawbacks. Working with the photopolymer can be difficult, and certain precautions must be taken to handle it. The resulting “green” pieces must be cleaned of liquid resin that has failed to solidify. Then, the pieces must be cured with a combination of temperature and UV light in order to attain their best mechanical properties. Also, similarly to FDM, the pieces often require support as they are being built. However, unlike with FDM in which an auxiliary extruder can provide a specialized, soluble support material, the supports in SLA need to be made of the resin available in the vat. When removing the supporting struts, some marks may remain on the surface of the piece, requiring manual sanding.

2.2.4. Facilities and materials

For this research, the FDM propeller was manufactured in Acrylonitrile Butadiene Styrene (ABS-M30) thermoplastic using a Stratasys F170 machine. The Z layer resolution was 125 μm, with the propeller being printed in layers parallel to the rotation plane. 100 % infill was selected in the slicer software. A limonene-soluble support material was also used to ensure proper attachment, which was removed in postprocessing.

Figure 4: Conceptual schematic of the SLA technology.

The SLS propeller was manufactured using a Formlabs Fuse 1 system. It features a 10 W ytterbium laser and is capable of a layer resolution of 110 μm, with a laser focal point of 200 μm. The employed material was Nylon 12. This is the only technology that requires no support or postprocessing other than cleaning the unsintered powder off the piece.

Finally, the SLA propellers were created with a Formlabs 3L printer. This machine features a variant of the SLA method called Low Force Stereolithography (LFS), which uses a roller and a flexible tray floor in order to ensure that only a very thin layer of resin is cured by the laser. Two 250 mW laser heads are used to speed up the process. The selected layer height was 50 μm, and the XY resolution was 25 μm for the standard Formlabs Grey v4 propeller. On the other hand, a layer height of 100 μm and an XY resolution

Figure 5: The propellers tested in this investigation. From left to right: FDM, SLS, SLA-grey and SLA-rigid versions. A zoomed view highlights the differences in surface quality.

249 of 25 μm was used for the Rigid 4000 resin propeller. The
 250 propellers were then cleaned with isopropyl alcohol and
 251 cured with the temperature and UV light cycles prescribed
 252 by the manufacturer. The support marks were manually
 253 sanded off.

254 In Fig. 5, the four propellers manufactured by each of
 255 the selected technologies are compared against each other.
 256 It can be seen how the FDM propeller features very clear
 257 layers, along with the paths of the filament (note especially
 258 how the shaft wall is created by a circular filament deposi-
 259 tion). The SLS propeller does not show any inhomogeneity,
 260 but a rougher surface can be clearly appreciated. Finally,
 261 the SLA propeller shows a smooth surface finish, appearing
 262 similar to a cast plastic piece.

263 Focusing on the material properties, Table 1 displays the
 264 main mechanical properties of the materials used in this
 265 study.

266 2.3. Experimental setup

267 In order to measure the noise emission of each propeller,
 268 an electric motor was installed in the anechoic chamber
 269 available at Laboratory 5K of the CMT - Clean Mobility &
 270 Thermofluids Institute. This chamber features a frequency
 271 cut-off of 100 Hz, and an available interior space of $7.5 \times$
 272 6.5×6 m. The non-influence of recirculation in this facility
 273 for 9-inch propellers measurements has been previously
 274 demonstrated [29]. The engine is an Avenger V3 2812-900
 275 kv and is governed by a V-GOOD 2-6S 40A Electronic Speed
 276 Controller (ESC). An Arduino UNO microcontroller, linked
 277 to a computer in the control room, commands the ESC.

278 To measure the acoustic emission, six Brüel & Kjær Type
 279 4190 free-field microphones are mounted in an arch, at a

Figure 6: Schematic of the experimental setup installed in the anechoic chamber at the CMT Institute.

Figure 7: FDM-manufactured propeller installed in the «Prof. Francisco Payri» wind tunnel.

280 distance from the propeller hub of 8.75 propeller diameters
 281 (D_p). The six microphones are mounted in increments of
 282 30° , starting from the vertical (upstream) of the propeller.
 283 They are simultaneously acquired by a PULSE Type 3560-D
 284 Data Acquisition System from Brüel & Kjær, also connected
 285 to the control room computer. A schematic of this setup is
 286 shown in Fig. 6.

287 After calibrating the microphones through a Brüel &
 288 Kjær Type 3541 pistonphone, measurements were made at
 289 164.5 rps (9870 rpm), capturing the acoustic signal for 2
 290 seconds.

291 The aerodynamic performance characterization of the
 292 different propellers was performed in the «Prof. Francisco
 293 Payri» wind tunnel at CMT. The test was carried out in the
 294 first test section of the wind tunnel reserved for low turbu-
 295 lence aerodynamic tests, through a custom 6-axis balance
 296 as shown in Fig. 7. The same motor and ESC as in the
 297 anechoic chamber setup have been used. The balance has
 298 been designed in-house and built using 6 Teda-Huntleigh
 299 Model 614 load cells at 70 degrees. Readings from the load
 300 cells are directly acquired through a National Instruments
 301 DAQ system.

302 After calibrating the load cells using reference weights,
 303 measurements were made at different rotational speeds,
 304 both with the tunnel stopped and at 10 m/s, to obtain data
 305 in hover and forward flight conditions. Ten repetitions of
 306 the measurements were performed for each propeller to
 307 ensure repeatability.

308 2.4. Numerical setup

309 In order to better understand the role of surface rough-
 310 ness and flexing under load on both aerodynamic and acous-
 311 tic performances, a numerical experiment was carried out,
 312 where advantage was taken of a previously validated numer-
 313 ical setup for a rigid, smooth propeller previously described
 314 by Serrano et al. [7]. In this work, the simulations were

315 performed following the same approach but using the com- 347
 316 mercial software *SimCenter STAR-CCM+* 2210. 348

317 As can be seen in Fig. 8, only the propeller is modeled. 349
 318 It is immersed in a spherical fluid domain with a radius 350
 319 of $7.5D_p$. A Moving Reference Frame (MRF) approach is 351
 320 used, with the rotating domain defined as a small cylinder 352
 321 around the propeller. An additional fixed cylinder is used 353
 322 as a refinement volume in order to improve the mesh quality 354
 323 in the propeller wake, bringing the total cell number to 2
 324 million. An image of the computational mesh is also shown
 325 in Fig. 8.

326 The first main modification of the existing model for 355
 327 this investigation was the consideration of Fluid-Structure 356
 328 Interaction (FSI), solving a Finite Element Model (FEM) of 357
 329 the propeller in coupling with the finite-volume fluid solver. 358

330 Given the nature of the said coupling, both solid and 359
 331 fluid physics are implemented, with a mesh of 400 thou- 360
 332 sand cells for the solid region. The simulations are treated 361
 333 as pseudo-stationary. To achieve this, an implicit unsteady 362
 334 model is employed with a sufficiently large time step, ensur- 363
 335 ing that steady-state conditions are reached at high simu- 364
 336 lation times. 365

337 The structural problem is solved using a nonlinear ge- 366
 338 ometry model, which accounts for large displacements and 367
 339 rotations by satisfying the equilibrium equations in the 368
 340 deformed configuration and iteratively updating the stiff- 369
 341 ness matrix via Newton’s method. A key implication is the 370
 342 treatment of follower forces, where forces, tractions, and 371
 343 pressures adjust their orientation as the structure deforms: 372
 344 force loads retain their vector components, traction loads 373
 345 preserve their direction while their resultant changes and 374
 346 pressure loads remain normal to the deformed surface. This 375

347 approach ensures a more accurate representation of slender 348
 349 structures undergoing large rotations with relatively small 350
 351 strains [30, 31]. 352

353 To ensure that the FSI simulation converges to a steady- 354
 355 state solution, Rayleigh damping is introduced to suppress 356
 357 structural oscillations. The damping matrix C is formulated 358
 359 as a linear combination of the mass and stiffness matrices 360
 361 [32], M and K respectively, as can be seen in Eq. 1. 362

$$C = \alpha M + \beta K, \quad (1)$$

363 where α is the mass-proportional damping coefficient and 364
 365 β is the stiffness-proportional damping coefficient. In this 366
 367 study, these coefficients are set to $\alpha=0.001$ Hz and $\beta=0.001$ 368
 369 s, calibrated based on the timescales of the observed oscil- 370
 371 lations. This choice ensures numerical stability and accel- 372
 373 erates convergence, allowing for an efficient evaluation of 373
 374 the steady-state structural response. However, it inherently 374
 375 suppresses dynamic instabilities, which could be relevant 375
 376 in cases of low structural stiffness or high rotational speeds. 376
 377 While such effects may play a role in certain operational 377
 378 regimes, their analysis falls beyond the scope of this study, 378
 379 which focuses on the steady-state behavior of the coupled 379
 380 system rather than transient or instability-driven phenom- 380
 381 ena, as studied in previous works [33, 34, 35, 36]. 381

382 The rotation is modeled using a Moving Reference Frame 383
 384 (MRF), which imposes a constant rotational flux in the 384
 385 conservation equations without physically deforming the 385
 386 mesh. This approach significantly reduces computational 386
 387 cost compared to a fully transient rotating mesh simulation, 387
 388 as can be seen in the work of Garofano-Soldado et al. [37] 388
 389 or Liu et al. [38]. 389

390 The fluid flow is governed by the Reynolds-Averaged 390
 391 Navier-Stokes (RANS) equations, discretized using second- 391
 392 order schemes for advection and diffusion terms. To model 392
 393 turbulence, the $k-\omega$ Shear Stress Transport (SST) model, 393
 394 proposed by Menter [39], is employed to compute the 394
 395 Reynolds stress tensor. This two-equation turbulence model 395
 396 is widely used in MRF and propeller simulations [37, 38]. 396

397 Although the flow remains essentially incompressible 397
 398 across all tested advance ratios, the fluid is modeled as an 398
 399 ideal gas to enhance numerical stability and ensure solver 399
 400 convergence. This approach helps avoid potential issues 400
 associated with solving the continuity equation in strictly in-
 compressible formulations, where small numerical pressure
 fluctuations can affect computational stability. Additionally,
 treating the fluid as an ideal gas provides greater flexibility
 in solving the conservation equations, reducing the risk
 of divergence without compromising accuracy within the
 evaluated range of conditions [40, 41].

401 The second study introduced a variable wall roughness 401
 402 via a modification of the wall treatment to sweep this param- 402
 403 eter and assess its influence on performance. This allows 403
 404 us to study the effect of both parameters in isolation to 404
 405 improve the understanding of the experimental results. 405

406 In order to modify the wall roughness, a roughness 406
 407 function is introduced (Eq. 3) [42]. Said function depends 407

Figure 8: Numerical domain with detail of the mesh.

401 on the roughness parameter R^+ , defined as in Eq. 2.

$$R^+ = \frac{r\rho u^*}{\mu} \quad (2)$$

$$f = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } R^+ \leq R_{smooth}^+ \\ \left[B \left(\frac{R^+ - R_{smooth}^+}{R_{rough}^+ - R_{smooth}^+} \right) + CR^+ \right]^a & \text{if } R_{smooth}^+ < R^+ < R_{rough}^+ \\ B + CR^+ & \text{if } R^+ > R_{rough}^+ \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

402 Where B, C, R_{smooth}^+ , and R_{rough}^+ are model coefficients (de-
403 fined in Table 2), r is the equivalent sand-grain roughness,
404 ρ the density, u^* the velocity scale, μ the dynamic viscosity,
405 and a is defined as in Eq. 4.

$$a = \sin \left[\frac{\pi}{2} \frac{\log(R^+/R_{smooth}^+)}{\log(R_{rough}^+/R_{smooth}^+)} \right] \quad (4)$$

406 Finally, the Hanson acoustic model [43] was used to
407 estimate the tonal noise numerically. This allows us to study
408 the influence of the material and surface roughness on the
409 tonal noise without having to carry out costly transient
410 simulations.

411 The Hanson model is a theoretical propeller noise formu-
412 lation that takes into account both the loading (Eq. 5) and
413 thickness (Eq. 6) noise sources and distributes them through
414 a helicoid. It has been recently used to study propellers'
415 noise [44] and compared with other acoustic analogies
416 [45, 46]. In this work, the input of the Hanson model is
417 the thrust and torque distributions along the blade span,
418 extracted from the steady CFD simulations.

$$P_{m_L} = \frac{mBM_t \sin \theta_r \exp [imB (\Omega S_r / c + (\phi' - (\pi/2)))]}{2\sqrt{2}\pi Y r_t (1 - M \cos \theta_r)} \times \int_{hub}^{tip} \left[\frac{\cos \theta'_r}{1 - M \cos \theta_r} \frac{dT}{dr} - \frac{1}{r^2 M_t r_t} \frac{dQ}{dr} \right] \exp(i\phi_s) J_{mB} \Psi_L dr \quad (5)$$

$$P_{m_T} = \frac{-\rho c^2 B \sin \theta_r \exp [imB (\Omega S_r / c + (\phi' - (\pi/2)))]}{4\sqrt{2}\pi (Y/D)(1 - M \cos \theta_r)} \times \int_{hub}^{tip} M_s^2 (h/b) \exp(i\phi_s) J_{mB} k_x^2 \Psi_V dr \quad (6)$$

419 Loading and thickness components are computed using
420 equations 5 and 6, where P_{m_L} and P_{m_T} are respectively the
421 loading and thickness components of the noise, dT and

B	C	R_{smooth}^+	R_{rough}^+
0	0.253	2.25	90

Table 2: Model coefficients for roughness function.

422 dQ are the thrust and torque of the differential element
423 of length dr , m is the harmonic number, B the number of
424 blades, M_t is the tip Mach number, θ the observer angle
425 relative to flight direction, θ_r the observer angle in retarded
426 reference frame and θ'_r the same angle but relative to the
427 propeller shaft axis, Ω the rotational velocity of the propeller,
428 S the distance of the observer from the propeller hub and
429 S_r the same distance in retarded reference frame, c the
430 speed of sound, ϕ the tangential angle and ϕ' the same
431 angle relative to the propeller shaft axis, Y the observer
432 distance from propeller axis, r_t the radius of the propeller, M
433 the freestream Mach number, r the non-dimensional radial
434 position, ϕ_s the phase shift due to sweep, ρ the density, D
435 the diameter of the propeller, M_s the section relative Mach
436 number, h the maximum airfoil thickness, and b the chord
437 of the blade at each section.

438 Finally, J_{mB} is defined as in Eq. 7, k_x is a wave number
439 defined by Equation 8, and Ψ_V and Ψ_L are non-dimensional
440 source transforms representing the effect of chord-wise non-
441 compactness. As suggested in Ref. [47] and used in Ref. [44,
442 46], a parabolic thickness distribution and a uniform lift
443 distribution were applied, defined in Equations 9 and 10.

$$J_{mB} = J_{mB} \left(\frac{mBrM_t \sin \theta'_r}{1 - M \cos \theta_r} \right) \quad (7)$$

$$k_x = \frac{2mBbM_t}{M_s(1 - M \cos \theta_r)} \quad (8)$$

$$\Psi_V(k_x) = \begin{cases} 2/3 & k_x = 0 \\ \frac{8}{k_x^2} \left[\frac{2}{k_x} \sin \frac{k_x}{2} - \cos \frac{k_x}{2} \right] & k_x \neq 0 \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

$$\Psi_L(k_x) = \begin{cases} 1 & k_x = 0 \\ \frac{2}{k_x} \sin \frac{k_x}{2} & k_x \neq 0 \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

3. Results & discussion

444 In this section, the experimental data will be presented
445 and discussed, and the results of the numerical models will
446 be used to draw further conclusions on the material and
447 surface roughness influence as isolated effects.

448 The performance data will be presented as dimensional
449 forces for the hover results (thrust and torque), and as non-
450 dimensional coefficients for the forward flight data, using
451 the definitions shown in Equation 11, where ρ_∞ represents
452 the undisturbed air density, n is the rotational speed of the
453 blade in rev/s, and D is the diameter of the propeller.
454

$$C_T = \frac{T}{\rho_\infty n^2 D^4} \quad C_P = \frac{P}{\rho_\infty n^3 D^5} \quad (11)$$

455 For the acoustic data, the spectra at different angular
456 positions will be shown, and the SPL at the BPF and OASPL
457 (Eq. 12) directivities will also be computed.

$$OASPL = 20 \cdot \log_{10} \left(\frac{P_{RMS}}{P_0} \right) \quad (12)$$

458 **3.1. Experimental campaign**

459 After manufacturing the different propellers using the
460 AM technologies described in section 2.2, these were in-

Figure 9: Thrust (top) and torque (bottom) vs rotational velocity in hover for each propeller measured in the wind tunnel.

Figure 10: C_T (top) and C_P (bottom) vs J for each propeller measured in the wind tunnel at a freestream velocity of $V_\infty = 10$ m/s.

461 stalled and tested in the anechoic chamber and wind tunnel
462 test benches, where the raw readings from the microphones
463 and the load cells, respectively, were recorded. As stated
464 before, at least 10 repetitions of the force measurements
465 were performed for each propeller to ensure repeatability.

466 The time evolution of thrust and torque during the exper-
467 iments was obtained using the load cell calibrations
468 performed before the measurement. Measurements at several
469 rotational speeds were carried out with the wind tunnel
470 stopped for the hover measurements, and with the wind
471 tunnel at 10 m/s for the advance operational conditions. For
472 each case, the average of the thrust and torque signals was
473 computed, and the standard deviation of said mean was ob-
474 tained, with the results being shown in Fig. 9 and 10. It can
475 be observed that at hover and low rotational speeds, there
476 is no significant difference in thrust between propellers.
477 In contrast, as the rotational speed increases, there is a
478 substantial increase in the performance of the propellers
479 made by SLA relative to the other two, with the difference
480 reaching up to 9.5% between the standard SLA and the
481 FDM propellers at the highest rotational speed.

482 On the other hand, the propeller manufactured by SLS
483 generates the highest torque, which is appreciable at all
484 rotational speeds. The other three propellers generate a sim-
485 ilar torque, being the FDM and SLA Rigid propellers slightly
486 higher than the SLA one at high rotational speeds. The
487 difference between the SLA and the SLS propeller torque
488 at the maximum rotational speed is up to 15%.

489 The findings regarding the SLA and SLS propellers are
490 consistent with current literature [17], where SLA pro-
491 pellers were found to produce a higher thrust and lower
492 torque at hover compared with SLS ones.

493 Regarding the measurements with mean flow, Fig. 10
494 shows the thrust and power coefficients evolution with re-
495 spect to the advance ratio. The advance ratio can be defined
496 as $J = Un/D$, where U is the flow velocity, n is the rotational
497 speed and D is the propeller diameter. It can be observed
498 that the differences in C_T are higher than the ones seen in
499 hover. Both SLA propellers produce a higher C_T at low val-
500 ues of J , as expected based on the hover results. However,
501 the slope of the SLA propellers is steeper than the other
502 two. Because of this, the thrust coefficient obtained at high
503 values of J is higher for the SLS and FDM propellers.

504 In terms of power coefficient, the hover trends seem to
505 continue for all the J range, with the SLS propeller being
506 the one with higher torque and the SLA propeller being the
507 one with a lower C_P . Nevertheless, the C_P of the SLA Rigid
508 propeller tends to get close to the SLS one at high advance
509 ratios.

510 It can be seen that there are no clear tendencies that can
511 be identified, as the two factors that have the greatest effect
512 on performance (material properties and surface finish)
513 operate simultaneously, hiding the individual effect. For
514 this reason, a numerical investigation will be carried out to
515 try to explain the findings obtained and to acquire a deeper
516 understanding of the underlying phenomena.

517 As for the noise generated by each of the propellers

518 manufactured with AM, the SPL at the BPF and OASPL
 519 directivity obtained around the propeller at a radius of
 520 2 meters are shown in Fig. 12. To expand the analysis,
 521 in Fig. 11, the spectrum of the sound signal recorded at
 522 -30 deg and 30 deg is presented.

523 It can be observed that at the first blade passing frequency,
 524 the sound level achieved is very similar among the
 525 four propellers in the -60 deg to 30 deg range, being slightly
 526 higher for the SLS propeller than for the other two. Near
 527 the axis of rotation, the difference increases, with the SLA
 528 Rigid propeller being the most silent one, with a difference
 529 of up to 8.75 dB.

530 This sound increase is also observed, with a greater noise
 531 increment, in the broadband noise at higher frequencies,
 532 where it can be seen how the SLS propeller generates a
 533 considerable noise increment, presumably due to the surface
 534 finish that causes the generation of a turbulent boundary
 535 layer. This phenomenon can be clearly observed in Fig. 11
 536 and explains the observed increase in OASPL directivity for
 537 the SLS propeller in Fig. 12 (down), with a difference of up
 538 to 5 dB depending on the angle.

539 In addition, it can be observed in Fig. 11 how at the
 540 shaft frequency (half the first blade passing frequency) a
 541 peak appears. This peak is higher in the case of the propellers
 542 manufactured in SLA, which would indicate that these are the
 543 propellers with the greatest geometrical difference between blades.
 544 This is probably due to the effect of hand sanding on the geometry.
 545 In fact, the SLA Rigid propeller shows an increase of up to 10 dB
 546 in the noise at

547 **Figure 11:** Frequency spectra for the -30° (top) and 30° (bot-
 548 tom) microphone positions hovering at 9870 rpm in the anechoic chamber.

549 **Figure 12:** Sound Pressure Level at the Blade Passing Frequency (top) and Overall Sound Pressure Level (bottom) directivity of the propellers at 9870 rpm.

547 the shaft frequency. This is consistent with the needed level
 548 of post-processing (higher in the Rigid case compared with
 549 the standard SLA one).

550 3.2. Numerical results

551 Regarding the numerical results, as stated before, steady
 552 simulations have been carried out, modifying the material
 553 Young's modulus (assuming isotropic materials) and
 554 modifying the surface roughness of the propeller (using a
 555 roughness function and assuming isotropic roughness)

556 3.2.1. Material influence

557 Regarding propeller performance, Figure 13 shows the
 558 thrust and power coefficients against advance ratio curves
 559 for different values of Young's moduli. It can be observed
 560 that at hover and low values of J there is a small increment
 561 in C_T for Young's moduli between 1 and 30 GPa. This
 562 tendency increases for lower values of E , with a difference
 563 of $\sim 22.5\%$ between the 0.05 GPa case and the rigid (30 GPa)
 564 one. Nevertheless, all curves converge to the same value
 565 when the advance ratio is increased, reducing the influence
 566 of the material. The same behavior can be observed for
 567 the power coefficient, with higher increments at hover (up
 568 to $\sim 58\%$ for the worst-case scenario). The gain in thrust
 569 produced by the influence of the material is found to be
 570 smaller than the increase in torque, resulting in reduced

571 efficiency and increased power consumption at hover and
 572 low values of J when reducing Young's modulus.

573 Figure 13 also shows a comparison between numerical
 574 results and experimental measurements. It can be noticed
 575 that, although the tendencies are correctly predicted, both
 576 coefficients are overestimated by the numerical model, the
 577 error being larger for the torque coefficient. This can be
 578 explained by the limitations of the numerical approach
 579 in accurately modeling the low Reynolds boundary layer
 580 and is not significantly higher than what may be expected
 581 compared to results from the literature [17].

582 This performance difference can be explained by the
 583 change in the effective geometry of the propeller. In Fig. 14,

Figure 13: Numerical predictions of C_T (top) and C_P (bottom) vs J for different values of E in a smooth propeller at $\Omega = 9870$ rpm, together with experimental data from the AM propellers.

Figure 14: Numerical prediction of θ along the propeller radius for different values of E at hover.

584 the theta distribution along the blade is shown for hover
 585 cases. It can be observed that a decrease in Young's moduli
 586 implies an increase of theta for almost the whole blade, al-
 587 though the theta value decreases near the hub. This increase
 588 in the twist distribution near the tip produces a change in
 589 the forces distribution, as illustrated by plotting the surface
 590 pressure coefficients in Fig. 16 for different values of E and
 591 J . The thrust and torque resulting from the different E
 592 values at different radii are shown in Fig. 15. An increase
 593 in the thrust and torque distributions from the middle of
 594 the blade onward is observed.

595 This variation in performance produces a change in the
 596 radiated noise, as predicted by the Hanson model, and can
 597 be seen in Fig. 17. However, the said increase in the sound
 598 pressure level is not noticeable for Young's moduli above
 599 1.25 GPa. This suggests that the increase in loading tonal
 600 noise due to the material's properties is not relevant for
 601 typical values of Young's modulus. It can also be observed
 602 that the directivity pattern observed for the tonal noise is
 603 consistent with the one shown in Fig. 12, with the highest
 604 value at the plane of rotation and higher SPL downstream
 605 than upstream of the propeller.

3.2.2. Roughness influence

606 For this section, the roughness height is increased to
 607 0.2 mm and 0.4 mm to analyze the influence of surface
 608 roughness on propeller performance and noise emissions.

609 In Fig. 18 (up), the values of the thrust coefficient are
 610 shown at different advance ratios. It can be seen that surface
 611

Figure 15: Numerical predictions of thrust (top) and torque (bottom) at different radii for different values of E in a smooth propeller at hover and $\Omega = 9870$ rpm.

Figure 16: Numerical prediction of the propeller deformation at different values of E and J compared against the original shape.

Figure 17: Numerical prediction of SPL variation as Young's moduli E are increased for a smooth propeller at hover and $\Omega = 9870$ rpm.

roughness produces a decrease in thrust obtained at every J value. Said decrease is smaller at higher advance ratios. No significant differences are observed between the two roughness heights. This decrease in the thrust coefficient leads to a better fit of the numerical results with respect to the experimental measurements.

The power tendency is more complex, as shown in Fig. 18 (down). The C_p at hover is increased by the influence of the surface roughness, with a difference of 8% and 9% for the 0.2 mm and 0.4 mm cases, respectively. However, when increasing the advance ratio, said tendency changes, obtaining slightly lower power coefficient values for the rough cases for $0.2 < J < 0.6$ and slightly higher C_p values at $J > 0.6$. Note that, as was the case with the flexibility study, due to the limitations in the modelling of the boundary layer, there is a significant difference of around 25% in magnitude with respect to the experimental data, which is in line with previous works in the literature

[17]. In this study from NASA/ONERA, a difference of up to 28.5% and 13.6% was found when comparing the torque at hover of an SLS propeller with Lattice-Boltzmann and Structured Navier-Stokes solvers, respectively.

As with Young's moduli, the change in roughness height produces a change in the forces distributions (as can be

Figure 18: Numerical predictions of C_T (top) and C_p (bottom) vs J for different surface roughness values in a rigid propeller at $V_\infty = 10$ m/s, together with experimental data from the AM propellers.

Figure 19: Numerical prediction of pressure coefficient at different blade sections and values of roughness and J .

Figure 20: Numerical predictions of thrust (top) and torque (bottom) at different radii in a rigid propeller at hover and $\Omega = 9870$ rpm.

Figure 21: Numerical prediction of SPL as surface roughness values are increased for a smooth propeller at hover and $\Omega = 9870$ rpm.

findings. On the other hand, the differences observed in C_p at the pressure side are not significant.

The said change in the pressure distribution along the blade produces an increase in the SPL emitted at the BPF, as can be observed in Fig. 21. In this case, the difference between the 0.2 mm and 0.4 mm cases is small, but the change between both and the smooth propeller is almost 0.5 dB. The same directivity pattern as for the material influence results and the experimental data is observed.

4. Summary & conclusions

In this work, an experimental campaign has been carried out, measuring the same propeller geometry manufactured with different AM technologies, including FDM, SLS, and SLA with two different materials.

It has been found that both the performance and noise emission of the propellers are dependent on the material

636 seen in Fig. 20) that explains the change in coefficients
 637 previously observed. In Fig. 19, the pressure coefficient
 638 along the chord at three different sections of the blade is
 639 shown. It can be observed that the suction peak is weaker
 640 for the roughness cases, with a bigger difference near the tip
 641 and at low advance ratios, which is consistent with previous

658 and manufacturing technology. At hover, the thrust produced by the SLA propellers is higher than its counterparts when rotating at higher rotational speeds. On the other hand, the SLS propeller shows higher torque at every velocity. For the forward flight operational conditions, it has been found that the SLA propellers exhibit a steeper C_T curve, while the SLS one produces the highest C_T at high advance ratios. Regarding the C_p , the hover tendencies seem to continue for the whole J range, except for the SLA rigid propeller, which matches the SLS values at high J .

659 Small differences in tonal noise have been found between the four propellers, with a noticeable increase at the shaft frequency peak for the SLA propellers, presumably due to the effect of hand sanding. Finally, the SLS propeller (the one with a higher and isotropic surface roughness) has been found to be the one with higher broadband noise emissions, which translates into a higher OASPL at all angles.

660 A numerical experiment has been carried out to investigate the isolated effects of the material properties and surface roughness on the results. It has been demonstrated that reducing E produces a change in the geometry, increasing the angle of attack and, consequently, increasing C_T and C_p at low advance ratios. This effect is not noticeable at sufficiently high J , producing a shift in the slope of the coefficient curves with respect to the advance ratio. On the other hand, taking into account surface roughness produces a reduction in C_T at every J due to a c_p reduction at the suction peak of the blade. The power coefficient is higher for almost the whole J range, except at $0.25 < J < 0.55$, where the value is slightly lower than the smooth propeller. As shown in Fig. 22, the efficiency of the propeller is, in general, reduced by both parameters, with the effect of roughness on performance greater than that of the properties of the material. This must be taken into account if the manufacture of un-postprocessed SLS propellers is considered.

661 Both modifications result in an increase in tonal noise, as captured by the Hanson model. Figure 23 shows the SPL

662 **Figure 23:** Numerical prediction of noise at different directions, including results from both parameter sweeps.

663 at the BPF variation for the two modifications taken into account. It can be observed that Young's modulus effect is not noticeable until the values of E are really low, while the roughness effect significantly increases the SPL, especially upstream of the propeller's plane.

664 This work represents a first step in understanding the influence of different Additive Manufacturing technologies on the performance and noise of low-Reynolds fixed-pitch propellers. Further work should be carried out to overcome the limitations of the present study and further extend the understanding of this phenomenon, including:

- 665 • An experimental campaign changing the resolution and orientation of the layers to analyze its influence.
- 666 • Consider the influence of anisotropic materials in the numerical simulations.
- 667 • Carry out transient CFD simulations with the FW-H analogy to evaluate possible transient phenomena not observed in this work.
- 668 • Use scale-resolving simulations to take into account broadband noise in numerical models, especially for the roughness influence.

669 **Figure 22:** Numerical prediction of propeller efficiency values against J as, including results from both parameter sweeps.

670 Conflict of interest statement

671 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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